

Design of Mobile Web-Based Tourism Marketing Information System Using SLDC Development (October 2019)

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Abstract—In this era of industry 4.0, where the human need for data access is increasing. As a result of these improvements, information systems are increasingly being used in various fields to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of a job. One of the improvements is to add an information system for tourist transportation, such as in the Sungai Pisang area. Fishermen on the Sungai Pisang often offer their *biduk* to take tourists to nearby islands for sightseeing. However, this is still lacking in taking advantage of the opportunities that exist. So designed a web-mobile-based information system that aims to increase the marketing of this *biduk* transportation service. Information systems are designed with SDLC (System Development Life Cycle) development methods and designed as user-friendly as possible so that tourists who want to book big dipper transportation services are more interested.

Index Terms—Data, efficiency, Effectiveness, Information System.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN Industry 4.0 era, human needs in data access are increasing. This is due to a shift in lifestyle towards a more developed one where all human activities are related to data. When talking about data, it is not spared that we discuss information systems. It is undeniable, the information system at this time is developing very quickly. The general public is starting to use information systems in work so that the work done is more effective and efficient than before.

Web-based applications are often used in improving the efficiency and effectiveness of a job. Examples of its application have been widely felt at this time, for example in buying and selling that is not only done in the market, but at this time there is already online buying and selling. Other examples such as learning during this pandemic where students do not have to go to the village to carry out learning, only need to go through their respective laptops.

Sungai Pisang is a village located in Bungus Teluk Kabung District, Padang. Most of the residents of this village work as fishermen, but they also often use their *biduk* to take tourists to island tourist sites so that the people there also take advantage

of this opportunity by opening *biduk* transportation services to nearby islands. However, only with this situation is still felt less in utilizing the opportunities that exist. This will be more effective and efficient if the dipper transportation service can be accessed through a mobile web-based application.

The purpose of creating this article is to design information system that can make it easier to order *biduk* transportation service in Pulau Pisang. Designing of this information systems based on the development of SDLC (System Development Life Cycle) systems.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Anggraeni (2017), information systems can be defined by the two of its words. System is a groups where the members is working together by a systematic and structured rule to form a unit that carried the goal. Information is data that is processed to be more useful for the recipient. Information systems is a regular combination of people, hardware, software, communicational network, and data resource that collect, change, and share information in an organization. According to Turban, information system is a something that has a function to collect, process, store, analysis, and share information for a specific purpose.

Information systems is an instrument consisting of various component that work together in a systematic and structured rule to achieve some goal of an organization. An organization can be determined as good or not organization by the performance of its information systems. Purpose of information system are provide information that can assist the management decision-making process, facilitate the implementation of daily operations, and provide appropriate information for parties outside of the organization, especially regarding to the issues of management transparency.

SDLC (System Development Life Cycle) is a description of an effort in designing a system that always rotating the phase. In other way, SDLC are stages of work aimed at produce an high quality system that suits with need. SDLC is a framework that contains the steps that must be followed to process the development of a software. This system contains a complete

plan for developing, maintaining, and replacing some specific software. According to Mulyani, SDLC is a logical process that used by a system analyst to develop an information system that involve requirement, validation, training, and system's owner.

Viewed by various sight, SDLC has many function, like as a tool of communication between developer team and stakeholder. SDLC also has a function to share roles and responsibilities between developer, designer, business analyst, and project manager clearly. Another function of SDLC is can provide a clear picture of input and output from one stage to the next.

SDLC contains some phases that were developed for a specific purpose. Here are the five phases that must be passed.

A. Planning

Planning phases emphasize on system development feasibility study aspect. There are some activity a this phase:

- Formation and consolidation of the development team.
- Define the object and scope of the development.
- Identify if there are some troubles that can be solved by system development.
- Determine and evaluate the strategy that will be used in system development.
- Determine the technology priority and app selection.

B. Analyst

In this phase, system will be analyzed how it will work. The result of analysis will be in form of deficiency and advantages, system function, and some updates that will be applied. Therefore, result of this of this phase are planning of project, schedule, cost estimation, and provision. Some activity that can be done in this phase are:

- Conduct a literature study to find a case that can be solved by the system.
- Brainstorming in development team about which case is best modeled with the system.
- Classified problem, opportunity, and solution that might be applied in that case.
- Analyze all needs to the system and create a system border.
- Define the system need.

C. Design

This stage will produce a prototype and several other outputs including documents containing the design, patterns, and components needed to realize the project. After the specification, then the design of the system as a continuation stage. This stage is the stage where all the results of analysis and discussion of system specifications are applied to the design or blueprint of a system. This stage is referred to as a blueprint, where the system is ready to be developed ranging from implementation, system analysis, to system support personnel to be developed.

In this stage, features and operations at system are described in detail. Activities will be seen in this phase:

- Analyzing interaction between object and function at system
- Analyzing data and create detailed schematics
- Designing user interface

D. Implementation

Implementation, namely implementing the design from previous stages and conducting trials. In this phase, the following activities are carried out:

- Creating a database according to the design scheme
- Creating app according to system design
- Testing and debugging

E. Maintaining

This phase is carried out by an admin who is appointed to keep the system able to operate correctly through the ability of the system to adapt itself according to needs.

III. DISCUSSION

Development of the information system for Sungai Pisang's biduk transportation service based on how user friendly the information system. This app use SDLC development method.

A. Planning

The plan in this case is to create or design an information system that can store all the data and information needed in the marketing of the transportation of the *biduk*. The design of information systems is not done at once, so research only focuses on the flow of information.

B. Analysis

Analysis of needs carried out by implementers of activities in the form of field studies (observations), data collection and information related to the design of the island tourism dipper marketing information system. The marketing information system designed must be user friendly so as not to confuse users in looking for the information needed.

C. Design

Based on the data and information collected, in this phase a database system is designed using MySQL that stores all the data and information needed in the design of the island tourism dipper marketing information system. This database is linked to a marketing information system making it easier for data storage and retrieval of necessary data.

Database design is done in accordance with the needs of marketing information systems taking into account the flow of data and information on the designed system. Database design consists of files with records that connect with a particular subject. A set of records consists of fields that are interconnected with logic. The preparation of a database's data structure is determined by the data model used. A data model is a collection of tools or emblems used to conceptually describe data.

In the design of marketing information systems this is used a relational data model because in a system designed consists of

several entities that are interconnected with each other. In the design of the database data model there are fields that connect the database building tables. File index design is used to improve data access performance. The indices used in system design are foreign key (non-unique key) and primary key (unique key). Foreign keys are used to create relationships between the tables used. Primary keys are used to prevent duplication of data so that information systems can be accessed more quickly by users.

D. Implementation

At this stage, the implementation of the *biduk* transportation marketing information system that has been designed to be used by the fishermen in marketing the island's tourism *biduk* transportation services. Fisherman are given training in the use of marketing information systems marketing island tourism dippers to increase the number of tourists in an effort to improve the economy of fisherman. In the implementation phase, the following activities are carried out:

- Transfer the website from localhost to server hosting.
- Creation of a database on hosting and application of user access rights on the database.
- Application testing and repair (debugging).

Furthermore, the operation of the marketing information system is carried out by *biduk* fishermen as admins who are trained to be able to operate marketing information systems effectively.

E. Maintaining

This maintenance is necessary to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of the performance of our existing systems so that their use can be optimal. The system does not rule out the possibility of changes or development as needed. This stage is carried out by an admin who is appointed to keep the system able to operate properly through the system's ability to adapt itself according to needs.

IV. CONCLUSION

Information systems is an instrument consisting of various component that work together in a systematic and structured rule to achieve some goal of an organization. Purpose of information system are provide information that can assist the management decision-making process, facilitate the implementation of daily operations, and provide appropriate information for parties outside of the organization, especially regarding to the issues of management transparency. SDLC are stages of work aimed at produce an high quality system that suits with need. SDLC contains some phases that were developed for a specific purpose, that is planning, analysis, design, implementation, and maintaining and it always cycling.

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